

1 **Human dendritic cells transmit Enterovirus A71 via heparan sulfates to target**
2 **cells independent of viral replication.**

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16 **Abstract**

17 Enterovirus A71 (EV-A71) is a causative agent of life-threatening neurological diseases in young
18 children. EV-A71 is highly infectious but it remains unclear how the virus disseminates from primary
19 entry sites, the mucosa of the respiratory tract or the intestine, to secondary replication sites, skin or
20 brain. Here we investigated the role of dendritic cells (DCs) in EV-A71 dissemination. DCs reside in
21 the mucosa of the airway and gut, and migrate to lymphoid tissues upon activation and therefore
22 could facilitate EV-A71 dissemination to secondary replication sites. Monocyte-derived DCs were not
23 permissive to different genotypes of EV-A71 but, notably, co-culture with EV-A71-susceptible RD99
24 cells led to very efficient infection of RD99 cells. Notably, EV-A71 transmission of DCs to RD99 was
25 independent of viral replication as a replication inhibitor did not affect transmission. Soluble heparin
26 blocked EV-A71 transmission by DCs to RD99 cells, in contrast to antibodies against known
27 attachment receptors DC-SIGN. These results strongly suggest that DCs might be a first target for EV-
28 A71 and involved in viral dissemination via heparan sulfates and heparin derivatives might be an
29 effective treatment to attenuate dissemination.

30 **Importance:** EV-A71 is an emerging neurotropic virus that is of emerging concern and can result in
31 polio-like illness. The exact mechanism of how EV-A71 results in neurological symptoms are
32 unknown. In particular, the early dissemination of the virus from primary replication sites (airway
33 and intestine) to secondary sites (CNS and skin) needs to be elucidated. There is evidence pointing
34 towards a role for Dendritic cells in EV-A71 transmission. Moreover, heparan sulfate (HS) binding
35 mutations are observed in patients with severe diseases. Therefore, we evaluated the potential role
36 of HS on DC in transmission. We find that HS are critical for transmitting EV-A71 by DC to target cells.
37 Our data is consistent with other clinical and in vitro observations highlighting the importance of HS
38 in EV-A71-induced disease.

39 **1. Introduction**

40

41 Enterovirus 71 (EV-A71) belongs to the *Picornaviridae* family and is the most prevalent causative
42 agent of hand, foot and mouth disease (HFMD) in young children [1-3]. In a small percentage of
43 infected children EV-A71 causes life-threatening neurological disease because of transmission from
44 the primary replication sites (respiratory or intestinal mucosa) to secondary target tissues, including
45 the central nervous system (CNS) [4, 5]. Consequently, EV-A71 infection may cause severe polio-like
46 acute paralysis, meningitis, and encephalitis [1-5]. At present, there is no antiviral treatment
47 available and only genotype specific vaccines are available in China [2, 3]. The primary entry sites for
48 EV-A71 are via the mucosa of the respiratory tract or the intestine. However, it is not known how EV-
49 A71 disseminates from these primary sites to secondary sites such as brain and skin [4, 6]. A potential
50 mechanism is through the interaction of EV-A71 with immune cells at the primary sites resulting in
51 dissemination into lymphoid tissue and subsequent secondary sites.

52 Dendritic cells (DCs) are antigen-presenting cells that reside in mucosal tissues and are therefore
53 among first immune cells to encounter pathogens upon infection [7, 8]. DCs are essential for inducing
54 immunity to invading pathogens as DCs capture and process pathogens for antigen presentation to
55 naive T cells [9, 10]. In turn, T cells induce a pathogen-tailored adaptive immune response. However,
56 multiple studies have shown that the function of DCs is subverted by several viruses e.g. measles
57 virus, hepatitis C virus (HCV), dengue virus (DENV) and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV),
58 resulting in viral dissemination mediated by DCs [11-14]. In the case of EV-A71, the role DCs play in
59 viral pathogenesis remains unclear. EV-A71 has been shown to productively infect immature DCs,
60 whereas DCs also mediate viral *trans*-infection via the attachment receptor DC-SIGN independent of
61 replication in DCs [15, 16]. Furthermore, the latter study implicated a role for DC-SIGN in capturing
62 and transferring the virus to target cells [16]. Moreover, there is clinical data to indicate that heparan

63 sulfate (HS) proteoglycans binding by EV-A71 may play a role in viral dissemination to secondary sites
64 but the relevance of HS binding to DC interaction remains to be elucidated [17, 18].

65 Therefore, in this study, we investigated the role of DCs in EV-A71 transmission and potential surface
66 molecules, including HS, that maybe involved in DC/EV-A71 interaction. Monocyte-derived DCs were
67 not permissive to infection with EV-A71 but efficiently transmitted EV-A71 to target cells
68 independent of viral replication in DCs. Soluble heparin blocked EV-A71 transmission by DCs. These
69 data support a role for DCs in viral transmission and highlight the importance of HS in EV-A71
70 pathogenesis and further research might benefit the search for new strategies for combating EV-A71
71 infection.

72

73 **2. Methods**

74

75 **2.1 Monocyte derived dendritic cells**

76 Peripheral blood monocytes were isolated from buffy coats of healthy donors (Sanquin) by
77 Lymphoprep (Axis-Shield) gradient, followed by Percoll (Amersham Biosciences) gradient steps.
78 Monocytes were differentiated into monocyte derived DCs in the presence of 500 U/mL IL-4
79 (Invitrogen) and 800 U/ml GM-CSF (Invitrogen) for 6 days in RPMI supplemented with 10% FCS
80 (Invitrogen), 10 U/mL penicillin(Invitrogen), 10 mg/mL streptomycin (Invitrogen), and 2 mM l-
81 glutamine (Lonza) as described before [19]. Dendritic cells were routinely analysed for surface
82 expression of DC-markers CD1a and DC-SIGN, and activation markers CD80, CD83 and CD86
83 (supplementary Figure 1).

84

85 **2.2 Enterovirus A71**

86 EV-A71 C1 91–480 was obtained from the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment,
87 Bilthoven, and strain C5 209-VN was previously provided by K. Mizuta (Yamagata Prefectural Institute
88 of Public Health, Japan) and Drs. N.T.T. Thao and P.V. Tu (Pasteur Institute Ho Chi Minh City,
89 Vietnam) [20]. EV-A71 (C1 and C5) were propagated in RD99 cells. Supernatant was filtrated, stored
90 at -80°C and thawed to room temperature (RT) before use. Infectious virus titers of the strains were
91 determined by the micro titration method on RD99 and were expressed as the 50% tissue culture
92 infectious dose (TCID50) [21].

93

94 **2.3 Cell line continuation**

95 RD99 cells were passaged weekly, after which cells were maintained in Eagle's minimum essential
96 medium (EMEM; Lonza) supplemented with 8% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Lonza), Pen-Strep (10.000
97 U/mL each; Lonza), 100x Non-Essential Amino Acids (NEAA; Sciencell), and L-glutamine (200 mM;
98 Lonza) in 0,85% NaCl.

99

100 **2.4 Transmission**

101 DCs were exposed to EV-A71 C1 and EV-A71 C5 at MOI 0.5 for 48 hours at 37°C either without the
102 presence of or in the presence of (1 hour at 37°C pre-incubation) replication inhibitor ribavirin (10
103 µM), anti-DC-SIGN (20 µg/µl), or an isotopic IgG1-kappa control (E-bioscience; 20 µg/µl). In addition,
104 EV-A71 C1 and EV-A71 C5 were pre-incubated with 5 mg/mL soluble heparin at 37°C for 2h for HS
105 proteoglycan binding assay. After 48 hours, DCs were washed extensively to remove unbound virus
106 and co-cultured with RD99 cells for 48 hours at 37°C. After co-culture, supernatant was collected and
107 cells were fixed in 4% para-formaldehyde at different time points (0h; 24h; 48h). Supernatant was
108 analysed using quantitative real-time PCR (RT-qPCR) whereas cells were analysed using flow
109 cytometry.

110

111 **2.5 Flow cytometry**

112 After fixation, cells were permeabilized in PBS supplemented with 0.5% saponin and 0.5% BSA for 10
113 min. Cells were stained with anti-EV-A71 (1:800, Geno) followed by Alexa 488-conjugated Donkey-
114 anti-Rabbit (1:200, Invitrogen) in combination with APC-conjugated CD1a (1:25, BD Biosciences). Cells
115 were quantified on a FACS Canto II (BD Biosciences) and results were analysed using FlowJo software.

116

117 **2.6 RNA isolation, cDNA synthesis and real-time PCR**

118 RNA from collected samples was extracted according to the manufacturer's protocol in the isolate II
119 RNA Mini Kit (Bioline). After RNA isolation, the eluates were reverse transcribed into cDNA using 20
120 mg/mL α -casein, 10x CMB1-buffer (pH 8.3), 40 mM dNTP's (10 mM each; Roche), 1.5 μ g/ μ l primer
121 random hexamers, 100 mM MgCl₂, 20-40 units/ μ l inhibitor RNasin (Promega), and 200 units/ μ l
122 SuperScript II (RNase H negative; ThermoFisher Scientific). The reverse transcription reactions were
123 performed for 30 minutes at 42°C at 600 rpm on a heat block (see Appendix F for preparation of the
124 cDNA synthesis mastermix). Before running the RT-qPCR (CFX), the cDNA mixtures were stored at -
125 20°C and thawed prior to RT-qPCR. During RT-qPCR, cDNA mixture was amplified with primers for EV-
126 A71 genome, 50 μ M EV-A71 forward, 5'-GGC CCT GAA TGC GGC TAA T-3', and 50 μ M EV-A71 reserve,
127 5'- GGG ATT GTC ACC ATA AGC C-3'. RT-qPCR was run using the Biorad CFX system with 2x SYBR
128 Green I Dye. RT-qPCR yielded C_q values and viral RNA copies were calculated with the equation
129 derived from the standard curve for Enterovirus primers: $y = -3.3968x + 38.939$ (R²=1). C_q was
130 substituted in place of y and solving x gives viral copy numbers.

131

132 **2.7 Statistical analysis**

133 Statistical analyses were performed using the independent T-test for unpaired observations using
134 GraphPad Prism 8 software. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

135

136 **2.8 Ethical statement**

137 This study was done in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the Academic Medical Center and
138 human material was obtained in accordance with the AMC Medical Ethics Review Committee. Buffy
139 coats obtained after blood donation (Sanquin) were handled anonymously.

140

141 **3. Results**

142

143 **3.1 Human dendritic cells transmit Enterovirus A71 genotypes C1 and C5 to target cells**

144 We investigated whether DCs can transmit EV-A71 to target cells. DCs were exposed to EV-A71 C1 or
145 EV-A71 C5 for 2 days and after extensive washing, co-cultured with RD99 cells for two days. Next, EV-
146 A71 C1 and EV-A71 C5 transmission was determined by flow cytometry (Figure 1A and 2A). DCs
147 express high levels of CD1a (Supplementary Figure 1A) and CD1a expression was used to distinguish
148 the DC population from RD99 cells. In turn, antibodies targeting EV-A71 were used to determine the
149 number of EV-A71 positive cells. EV-A71 C1 and EV-A71 C5 positive RD99 cells were observed after
150 24h post transmission (p.t.) while the number of EV-A71 C1 and EV-A71 C5 positive RD99 cells
151 significantly increased at 48h p.t. (Figure 1B and 2B), indicating transmission of EV-A71 from DCs to
152 RD99. Strikingly, pre-incubation of DCs with ribavirin, a known inhibitor of EV-A71 [22, 23], did not
153 block transmission, suggesting that viral transmission to RD99 cells is independent of EV-A71
154 replication in DCs (Figure 1B and 2B). Ribavirin functionality was determined in RD99 cells
155 (Supplementary Figure 1B, C). Next, the total number of EV-A71 RNA copies was determined in the

156 supernatant of DCs co-culture by quantitative PCR. EV-A71 C1 and C5 RNA copies increased over all
157 time points and treatment of DCs with ribavirin did not affect virus production (Figure 1C and 2C).
158 Lastly, EV-A71 transmission was determined by assessing the cytopathic effect (CPE) by microscopy.
159 Co-culture of RD99 cells with EV-A71-treated DCs induced a strong CPE in contrast to mock infection
160 (Figure 1D and 2D). Furthermore, an equivalent CPE was observed when ribavirin was used to block
161 infection of DCs. Altogether, these data strongly suggest that DCs were able to transmit different
162 genotypes of EV-A71 to target cells independent of viral replication in DCs.

163

164 **3.2 Human dendritic cells are not permissive to EV-A71 infection**

165 Next, we investigated whether EV-A71 C1 and EV-A71 C5 could be detected in DCs. Importantly, no
166 infection of EV-A71 in DCs was observed for both genotypes at 48h post infection (p.i.) (Figure 3A and
167 3B). Moreover, co-culture of DCs with RD99 cells did not lead to infection of DCs at 24h p.t (72h p.i.
168 Figure 3A and 3B). In addition, direct infection of DCs alone did not result in infection by EV-A71 C1
169 and EV-A71 C5 as determined by flow cytometry and quantitative PCR (Supplementary Figure 2).
170 These results strongly suggest that DCs are not susceptible to EV-A71 infection following early
171 encounters with the virus but are still able to efficiently transmit the virus to target cells.

172

173 **3.3 Heparan sulfates are involved in EV-A71 transmission by DCs**

174 Next, we investigated the receptors involved in virus transmission by DCs using blocking antibodies
175 against several putative viral receptors. Several receptors already have been implicated in EV-A71
176 infection and transmission of DCs including DC-SIGN [15, 16, 24-26]. In addition, HS are implicated
177 EV-A71 infection, as potential attachment receptors [17, 18]. HS are expressed in DCs, and we used
178 soluble heparin to block HS bindings sites on EV-A71. Antibodies against DC-SIGN did not block EV-
179 A71 transmission by DCs. Strikingly, pre-incubation of EV-A71 C1 and EV-A71 C5 with soluble heparin
180 abrogated transmission of both strains at 24h and 48h to background levels (Figure 4B and 5B).
181 Similarly, EV-A71 RNA copies in the supernatant increased over time in DC-RD99 co-cultures but

182 soluble heparin significantly decreased EV-A71 copies compared to the untreated control (Figure 4C
183 and 5C). These results strongly suggest that HS are involved transmission of both EV-A71 C1 and C5
184 genotypes by DCs.

185

186 **4. Discussion**

187 Our data strongly suggests that DCs are not susceptible to EV-A71 infection but can efficiently
188 transmit captured virus to target cells. Previous research by *Ren et al.*, 2014 showed *trans*-
189 transmission of EV-A71 to target cells by DCs using short (4h) DC/EV-A71 incubation periods [16].
190 However, this short duration is not sufficient to assess *cis*-transmission warranting longer incubation
191 periods such as the 48h used in our study. Exposing the DCs to EV-A71 in the presence of viral
192 replication inhibitor, ribavirin, for this longer duration still resulted in transmission of the virus to
193 target cells. Additionally, we have showed that no EV-A71 could be detected in DCs up to 72h p.i.
194 (24h p.t.), confirming that DCs are not permissive to infection. This was confirmed by the lack of EV-
195 A71 replication in DCs alone when exposed to EV-A71 C1 and C5. This is in contrast to the study of *Lin*
196 *et al.*, 2009 who report active replication of EV-A71 in DCs. However, the viral titre in the study by *Lin*
197 *et al.*, 2009 declined steadily over 48h suggesting that DCs retain EV-A71 but active infection was not
198 conclusive.

199 Next, to assess the potential receptors involved in the *trans*-transmission of EV-A71 by DCs, we
200 evaluated the role of DC-SIGN and HS. DC-SIGN has been shown to be involved for *trans*-transmission
201 of EV-A71 by DCs. However, in our study, treatment of DCs with anti-DC-SIGN antibodies did not
202 result in inhibition. The differences in the finding could be due to the different EV-A71 strains or
203 differences in exposure times used in studies. Clinical studies have shown an important role for DC-
204 SIGN in disease outcome as polymorphisms in DC-SIGN and high levels of soluble DC-SIGN are
205 associated with more severe HFMD outcome as the virus is less efficiently cleared [7, 8].

206 Interestingly, our results show a complete abrogation of EV-A71 transmission when the virus is pre-
207 incubated with soluble heparin both in flow cytometry and RT-qPCR results. As HS is seen as primarily
208 an attachment, rather than entry, receptor of EV-A71, the role of HS in EV-A71 transmission may be
209 more prominent compared to earlier studies with PSGL-1 or DC-SIGN. HS-binding mutations in VP-1
210 of EV-A71 appear to be important for neurotropism of EV-A71 [27]. HS-binding mutations such as
211 glutamine at 145Q are associated with severe neurological disease in human. Moreover, *Tseligka and*
212 *colleagues* showed intrahost HS-binding adaptations leading to HS-binding variants being isolated
213 from secondary infection sites [27]. Thus, interaction of HS-binding variants with DCs may play a role
214 in their dissemination to secondary target sites. Comparison of HS-binding and non-HS-binding
215 variants as well as their transmission by DCs to susceptible models such as brain organoids will be of
216 importance to further elucidate this dependence. Most importantly, should these findings hold true,
217 low molecular weight heparin could be an option to prevent dissemination of virus to secondary sites
218 in infected infants. With the lack of an effective treatment or vaccine, unravelling this mechanism
219 might prove valuable in combating EV-A71 related pathologies.

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221

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225

226 **6. Author contributions**

227

228 **LCH, MSB** and **AS** designed, performed and interpreted most experiments and prepared the
229 manuscript. **LCH, MSB, DP, KCW, THBG** and **AS**, participated in discussion of the data. **TBHG** and **AS**
230 supervised all aspects of the project.

231

232 **7. Competing interests**

233

234 The authors declare no competing interests.

235 **8. References**

236

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294

295 **9. Figure legends**

296 **Figure 1 | Human dendritic cells transmit EV-A71 C1 to target cells. A-D.** DCs were exposed to
297 EV-A71 C1 (MOI 0.5) for two days, and after extensive washing co-cultured with RD99 cells. DCs were
298 treated with Ribavirin (RBV; 10 μ M) to control for a replicating infection in DCs during transmission.
299 After co-culture, supernatant and cells were collected at different time points and analysed by RT-
300 qPCR and flow cytometry, respectively. **(A-C)** Flow cytometry analyses of DC transmission to RD999 is
301 shown for one representative donor (A) and combined data for different donors on infection of
302 CD1a-negative RD99 cells by flow cytometry (B, N=4) and virus production in co-culture (**C, N=4**). The
303 symbols represent independent donors mean \pm s.d. (flow cytometry) or mean \pm SEM (RT-qPCR) of
304 duplicates. **(D)** Images show the morphological changes of RD99 cells indicating the cytopathic
305 effects 48h after incubation with a representative DC donor.

306 **Figure 2 | Human dendritic cells transmit EV-A71 C5 to target cells. A-D.** Transmission
307 experiments with EV-A71 C5 are performed as described in Figure 1. **(A)** Populations plots of one
308 representative donor are shown to indicate the percentages of gated cells, **(B, N=4)** followed by the
309 combined percentage of EV-A71 VP1 positive RD99 cell (CD1a-negative population) as detected by
310 flow cytometry and **(C, N=4)** the total amount of viral copies as detected by RT-qPCR. The symbols
311 represent independent donors mean \pm s.d. (flow cytometry) or mean \pm SEM (RT-qPCR) of duplicates.
312 **(D)** Images show the morphological changes of RD99 cells indicating the cytopathic effects 48h after
313 incubation with a representative DC donor.

314 **Figure 3 | Human dendritic cells transmit EV-A71 C1 to target cells. A-D.** DCs were exposed to
315 EV-A71 C1 or EV-A71 C5 (MOI 0.5) for two days in the absence or presence of replication inhibitor
316 ribavirin (10 μ M). Next, DCs were washed extensively and co-cultured with RD99 cells. DCs from
317 figure 1 & 2 as analysed by were collected and analysed by flow cytometry respectively at the
318 moment of co-culture (48h) or one day (72h) after transmission (96h). **(A)** Populations plots of one
319 representative DC donor are shown to indicate the percentages of gated cells followed by the
320 combined percentage of **(B, N=4)** EV-A71 C1 and **(C, N=3)** EV-A71 C5 in the DC population (CD1a-
321 positive population) as determined by flow cytometry. The symbols represent independent donors
322 mean \pm s.d. of duplicates.

323 **Figure 4 | Heparan sulfates are involved in EV-A71 C1 transmission by DCs. A-D.**

324 Transmission experiments with EV-A71 C1 are performed as described in Figure 1. DCs were pre-
325 incubated with either anti-DC-SIGN antibodies or soluble heparin (5 mg/mL). After co-culture,
326 supernatant and cells were collected at different time points, and analysed by RT-qPCR and flow
327 cytometry, respectively **(A)** Populations plots of one representative DC donor are shown to indicate
328 the percentages of gated cells, **(B, N=4)** followed by the combined percentage of EV-A71 C1 positive
329 cells RD99 cells (CD1a-negative population) as determined by flow cytometry, **(C, N=4)** and the total
330 amount of viral copies as detected by real-time PCR. The symbols represent independent donors
331 mean \pm s.d. (flow cytometry) or mean \pm SEM (RT-qPCR) of duplicates. **(D)** Images are included to
332 show the morphological changes of RD99 cells 48h after incubation with a representative DC donor.

333

334

335 **Figure 5 | Heparan sulfates are involved in EV-A71 C5 transmission by DCs. A-D.**
336 Transmission experiments with EV-A71 C5 are performed as described in Figure 4. (A) Populations
337 plots of one representative DC donor are shown to indicate the percentages of gated cells, (B, N=4)
338 followed by the combined percentage of EV-A71 C5 positive cells RD99 cells (CD1a-negative
339 population) as determined by flow cytometry, (C, N=4) and the total amount of viral copies as
340 detected by real-time PCR. The symbols represent independent donors mean \pm s.d. (flow cytometry)
341 or mean \pm SEM (RT-qPCR) of duplicates. (D) Images are included to show the morphological changes
342 of RD99 cells 48h after incubation with a representative DC donor.

EV-A71 C1 (MOI 0.5)

EV-A71 C5 (MOI 0.5)